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China's Rapid Strides in Aviation Industry: Implications for Indian Air Force

Abstract

Until the 1990s, it was no secret that China possessed one of the most laggard and technologically backward defence industries in the world. But Deng Xiaoping's orchestrated plans of channelling private funds into defence R&D provided the required impetus for the growth of the aviation industry in China. After nearly three decades of investment, reorganisation, and acquisition of broad foreign technology, China's aviation sector is now well on its way to making China one of the top two or three global air and space powers by the 2020s.

In view of the changing geo-strategic scenario, increased asymmetry in terms of air power of China vis-a-vis India, it is an imperative to examine the implications of the burgeoning Chinese air power capability for Indian Air Force in the medium- as well as the long-term. This examination delves into a reality check on the Chinese aviation industry through an Indian prism and the likely air power capabilities which China likely to acquire through its proactive aviation industries. The Indian government is aware of this fact and new incentives have already been introduced to rejuvenate Indian aviation industry; however, the present incentives of 'Make in India' and strategic partnership need to be recapitulated further.

Introduction

China has emerged as a major regional power with clear aspirations to be a global power soon. Comprehensive military modernisation programmes supplemented with sustained economic, scientific and technological developments have substantially elevated China's international profile. Post-

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independence, the Chinese had set up a defence infrastructure modelled on the lines of the Soviet Union but with Chinese characteristics. Therefore, the arms industries over the years have been able to produce a wide range of conventional weapon systems like tanks, small arms, armoured vehicles, artillery, missiles, bombers, fighters and naval vessels, which though obsolete when compared with the West, were nevertheless, manufactured indigenously.

Until the 1990s, it was no secret that China possessed one of the most laggard and technologically backward defence industries in the world. Most indigenously developed weapon systems were of inferior quality and trailing way behind the west by at least a decade and a half, if not more. However, with Deng's orchestrated plans of channelling private funds into defence R&D, provided the required impetus for the growth of the Aviation Industry in China. After nearly three decades of investment, reorganisation, and acquisition of broad foreign technology, China's aviation sector is now well on its way to making China one of the top two or three global air and space powers by the 2020s. China is now producing two fifth-generation fighters and the Chinese-made, carrier-based, e2 fighter is undergoing trials. These fighters are equipped with Chinese-made world class precision air-to-air and ground attack weapons. China employs more than 1,20,000 personnel in aviation related R&D, making it the largest in the world.

Hence, Chinese aviation industry, which was earlier impaired by the unwillingness of the conservative leaders to implement path-breaking reforms, has been reversed in this millennium and the industry is fast consolidating to be able to rub shoulders with the top ranks in the global aviation sector.¹ It has been observed that there has been a definite shift in the guiding principle driving the aviation industry, from earlier obsession for quantity to now quality, from being a technology imitator to eventually becoming an enabler, with a major thrust on the sector to transcend and match up to the global standards, if not by 2020 then at least by 2030.

However, China's emergence as a military superpower against the backdrop of its propensity for military conflict over contentious issues raises strategic uncertainties and concerns about China's future military directions. It's truism that the twenty-first century future, of not just Asia, but the entire world, will be significantly determined by the relationship between the globe's two fastest growing economies, China and India. As most observers know, there have for long been kinks in the political-military relationship between the two countries. India, despite being amongst the top ten defence spenders in the world, continues to procure over 70 percent of its equipment needs from abroad. As a result,

India is unable to extract the maximum benefit for its economy from the expansion cycle driven by the modernisation plan of its aviation industry. India must rapidly shift focus from acquiring platforms to developing capabilities, absorb R&D as an integral part of the system. The aviation industry in India needs to strategize by becoming a part of the global supply chain which can, not only invigorate the aviation industry, but also bring along with it better management and financial practices, improve efficiency and produce better quality products for the end user.

The Puzzle, Assumption, Rationale

The dwindling strength of fighters in the Indian Air Force (IAF) due to delayed and inadequate acquisitions, over-reliance on imports and the slow growth of indigenous Indian aviation industry, in contrast with rapid strides by the aviation industries of China, has resulted in a greater asymmetry in terms of air power capability between the two countries and imposes a greater threat to IAF in case of any future conflict.

Comparison of the force levels as they exist today and the extended sphere of influence that China and India will acquire through planned inductions and production capabilities of their aviation industries in the future, IAF will not be able to match Chinese air power capabilities by 2030.

With recent changes in the geo-political scenario in the Indian sub-continent, Sino-Indian relationship is facing new challenges in the form of 'Doklam' and rising border issues of transgression in Ladakh as well as in Arunachal sector. In view of this changing scenario, increased asymmetry in terms of airpower (of China with respect to India, which has been acquired by virtue of its thriving Chinese aviation industry in comparison to the slow and weak Indian aviation industry) needs to be updated to examine the threat it poses to IAF in the medium as well as the long terms. This examination entails a reality check on Chinese aviation industry through an Indian prism and the likely airpower capabilities which China is going to acquire through these aviation industries. The Indian government is already aware of this fact and new incentives have already been introduced to rejuvenate Indian Aviation Industry; the present incentives of 'Make in India' and strategic partnership need to be recapitulated to provoke qualitative as well as quantitative analysis of air power capabilities of both countries in a present day scenario and thus draw the future with respect to future plans.

The article attempts to enquire upon the modernisation of aviation industries of China in terms of recent developments with prime focus on the military aircraft in general and fighter aircraft in particular. On similar lines, Indian aviation

industry is analysed in terms of ongoing fighter air craft projects as well as peek into the future after implementation of new incentives by the current Indian government to predict likely airpower capabilities between the two countries by 2030.

China's Aviation Industry: Evolution and Revolution

China has recognised the strategic reality that in its move upwards to military superpower status, it should contend not only with the US but also with many competing regional powers for the same power status and the main complicating factors in this are its territorial disputes with them, which could hinder China's military rise. It has also realised that such regional powers could be induced to gravitate towards the United States if China continues to exploit border disputes as strategic pressure points. For the last two decades, China has deeply studied the military developments that are taking place across the world, with a primary focus on the United States. Seminal moments like the co-ordination of the US air campaign during operation "Desert Storm" were wake-up calls for Beijing to modernise its military. At the same time, the increasingly global lines of communication that sustain the Chinese economy concurrently began to extend beyond the People's Liberation Army (PLA)'s ability to project force. As China moved into the twenty-first century, its military was intent upon following and integrating the teachings of the western military powers. From developing the JF-17 fighter jet, which is equipped with the Russian engine, to bringing the new J-10 fighter on line equipped with a domestic engine, China has already refined its domestic military aviation industry. The ability to design and produce indigenously, two fighter aircrafts possibly equivalent to the early F-35 is noteworthy.²

Emergence as an economic superpower was not a challenging task for China but it faced substantial number of challenges in its pursuit towards achieving the same status in the field of aviation. In order to prove its hegemony in the sub-continent, supremacy in terms of 'Air Power' was the first priority for China. China's aviation industry was plagued by problems of inefficiency, redundant leadership, and overlapping organizational and bureaucratic structures. However, with China's strong economy and prioritized military development, such problems were eradicated in due course of time. With the inception of reforms and opening-up of PLA modernisation plans, problems in China's outdated aviation industry began to surface, prompting the leadership of People's Republic of China (PRC) to reinstate a series of reforms. In May 2008, China established the Commercial Aircraft Corporation of China Ltd. (COMAC), and in November 2008, China merged China Aviation Industry Corporation I (AVIC I) and China

Aviation Industry Corporation II (AVIC II) to found the China Aviation Industry Corporation (AVIC). This overhaul of the aviation sector was an indication that the pace of development and reform in China's aviation industry is picking up. Therefore, China's determination and injection of resources into the industry should not be underestimated by the outside world.

In 1991, the Soviet Union collapsed and the environment changed to China's advantage. A desperately cash-deficient Russia offered to sell modern aircraft, weapons and high-tech equipment to China whose booming economy could provide ready dollars. Many jobless scientists, experts and technicians from the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) were also available for hire. Israel transferred designs and production technology to manufacture the Lavi jet fighter in the Chengdu Aircraft Industry Company and thus began development of the J-10³. The JF-17 was also being developed in collaboration with Pakistan as a result of these steps. Chinese aviation made good progress in all fields except aero-engines and fire control radars. These shortcomings are being addressed and China is reported to be investing in aero-engine R&D to cover this technology gap. China has transformed itself from a country that imports the assembly line of fourth generation fighters to a country that can now export the assembly line of fifth generation fighters.

China's Transformation: Imitator to Creator

China's efforts to acquire, produce, and develop fighter aircraft and related technology gained sufficient momentum by the early 1990s. China's quest to develop advanced fighter aircraft which required the most sophisticated level of aerospace technology and presented unique design and fabrication challenges for its military aviation industry was addressed through a series of organizational reforms. Significant advances made in the areas of material science, avionics and power engines from the defence arena have crossed over to the production of civilian aircraft. Over the years, China had been using 'Russians' as a quick fix solution during crisis and as a panacea for People's Liberation Army Air Force (PLAAF)'s depleting stock of sophisticated aircraft. In the early years of transition, there was technology flow from the west through the 'Peace Pearl' programme, as well as notable assistance from Israel and Italy. The Israel Aerospace Industry (IAI) was instrumental in providing significant exposure to China in the realm of high end technology through the 1980s and 1990s, which created concern in the American establishment. As a result, Israel was coerced into abandoning the sale of the Phalcon AWACS to China in 2000.

China's growing insecurity because of an overt dependence on the West for high end technology was reaffirmed by its belief, when it declared that there

was no substitute for self-reliance. Therefore, China had to quickly transmute from walking on four legs to standing on one's own two feet. Hence, it was left with no choice other than to develop a robust R&D infrastructure to counter its seasonal isolations from the West, which had been displaying a systematic 'on and off' strategy, with some regularity, particularly when it came to the business of providing assistance in high end technology to China. As a result, China decided to strengthen its R&D base by churning out large numbers of graduates and engineers in the mid-1990s and providing them incentives to travel overseas for higher education. The intention was to utilise the qualified human resource which could later be re-injected into the system to augment the capability of some of the strategic industries and help to build a strong R&D base for China. China's growing domestic capability has made rapid advances since the 1990s when China was mostly producing copies of obsolete Soviet era air craft.

Gaps in technological capabilities were filled by building alliances with foreign components and 'parts' manufacturers who are also suppliers or partners of Boeing and Airbus. Also, China has been able to entice foreign competitors to voluntarily transfer knowhow, using its huge domestic market as leverage. The practice of outsourcing has also worked to the advantage of Chinese aircraft makers. Indeed, the proliferation of foreign component and part suppliers allow Chinese aircraft makers to easily source what they are unable to produce. Presently, China's aviation industry is producing two indigenous fourth generation fighters, the J-10 and J-11. China's is the only country in the world who is pursuing two most prominent fifth generation stealth fighter projects, which are J-20 and J-31. Not much is available about the performance of J-20 and J-31, but how advanced they are, as compared to the western and Russian stealth fighters is yet to be seen in times to come.

Fifth Generation Fighters

The mantle of fifth, or even sixth, generation multirole combat aircraft (MRCA) development has unquestionably moved east, with no less than five Asian countries involved in indigenous future MRCA projects, and the leader of the field is China. With a \$ 132 billion defence budget, an increase of 12.2 percent over the previous year, China is forging ahead with the development of a range of advanced MRCA for PLAAF. These include:

- (a) **J-20:** Chengdu Aircraft Corporation (CAC) J-20, a fifth generation MRCA flew its maiden flight in 2011. This large twin-engine, twin-fin, canard/delta-wing aircraft, has internal weapons bays capable of housing air-to-air or air-to-ground weapons plus an additional single missile bay in each engine intake trunk; to date, six prototypes, powered by

Russian AL-31F afterburning turbofans have been flown while production of the J-20 may commence in 2017⁴. China was initially projected to have fifth generation aircraft by 2020. PLAAF Deputy Commander Gen He Weirong stated that this fighter will enter service between 2017 and 2019.⁵ He also said that the planes in development will match or exceed the capability of similar jets in existence today. Just before Gen He's statement, Chinese internet sources stated a prototype of the fifth-generation fighter that started flying in 2010, albeit with a version of the 12/13 ton thrust WS 10A turbo fan in lieu of the 'not yet ready' 15 ton thrust engine.

It was also noted that China could acquire up to 300 of these fighters, which will have the "4 S" capabilities: stealth, super cruise, super manoeuvrability and short take-off. Both the Shenyang Aircraft Company 601 Aero Design Institute and the Chengdu Aircraft Company 611 Aero Design Institute were then allotted work in the "203" Programme. Both are thought to have been working on heavy twin engine stealthy and highly manoeuvrable designs to compete with the US and Russian fifth generation fighters. Chengdu has usually been associated with a twin-engine canard delta design. China is expected to have a handful of fifth generation fighters in service by 2020.⁶ The general design concept of the J-XX is that of a fifth-generation fighter.

- (b) J-31:** As reported by the Chinese state media, China has tested the latest version of its fifth generation stealth fighter in an attempt to end the West's monopoly on the world's most advanced warplanes. These tests come as the nation flexes its military muscles, sending its sole aircraft carrier the Liaoning into the western Pacific to lead drills there for the first time. The newest version of the J-31- now renamed the FC-31 Gyr Falcon took to the air for the first time on 27 Dec 2016. The so-called "fifth generation" twin-engine fighter is China's answer to the US F-35, the world's most technically advanced fighter. The new FC-31 has "better stealth capabilities, improved electronic equipment and larger payload capacity" than the previous version which debuted in October 2012, according to aviation expert Wu Peixin. Changes were made to the airframe, wings and vertical tails which make it leaner, lighter and more manoeuvrable. The fighter is manufactured by Shenyang Aircraft Corp, a subsidiary of the AVIC. When completed the FC-31 will become the country's second fifth generation fighter after the J-20, which was put on its first public performance at the Zhuhai Air Show in November 2016.⁷

There is also a possibility that China could have a programme for other fifth generation fighters, perhaps to include a medium weight fighter to complement its reported heavyweight fighter programme. Nonetheless, as the capabilities of China's aviation industry begin to approach those of the rest of the world, the latecomer's advantage will no longer be obtained. In the absence of an indigenous combat aircraft programme, Israel is unlikely to be able to provide China with state-of-the-art aviation technologies outside of such key sub-systems as avionics. Thus, further improvements in the capabilities of China's aviation industry will increasingly depend on its indigenous capacity for technological innovation. From 1990 through 2010, specific to the PLAAF, the implications of a growing fleet of fourth generation fighter aircraft hold two potential meanings. For the strategic intentions of China, they represent a natural replacement for 40-year old fighters, thus, adding to the national prestige. To current military analysts, the increased lethality represents a force that can potentially skew the entire regional balance of power. The move from the Chinese Air Force of over 5,000 aircraft to one of 1,617, approximately 500 of which are modern, changes the range of strategic employment options available to the PRC.

China's Modern Air Force: Implications in IAF

Incidentally, there is an interesting relationship between the Hindustan Aeronautics Ltd (then Hindustan Aircraft Ltd.) and the Chinese Aviation Industry, historically. Douglas Pawley, a private American businessman, who had set up a number of aircraft factories in China in the 1930s was looking to wind them down due to the advancing Japanese forces invading the country. It was William D Pawley who, through a chance meeting with Walchand Hirachand, an Indian businessman, in an airliner, flying from the US, decided to transfer his operations to India and set up a joint venture by establishing the first aircraft factory in India in 1939, the Hindustan Aircraft Ltd. (now Hindustan Aeronautics Ltd.).⁸ Comparative analysis based on modern sophisticated Chinese Air Force vis-a-vis the present-day combat capabilities of IAF need to be revisited to access the threat scenario in the Asian subcontinent. Based on the fact that Airpower strategy and the aviation industry have advanced together, insight into what Airpower strategy, both countries might foresee in future becomes even more relevant. Thereafter, it peeks into the current status of IAF with focus onto its Indigenous fighter project "Tejas" as well as the future of India's fifth generation fighter projects.

With an analysis of planned inductions as well futuristic production capability of its aviation industry, comprehensive military power can be calculated with respect to both the countries. By virtue of SWOT analysis (strength, weakness,

opportunity, threat), application of Chinese air power against India was analysed wherein it was assessed that current Chinese air power can be used from air force bases located in Tibet but still would not pose an unmanageable threat to the IAF. Indeed, given the inadequacy of secure and hard shelters for its fighters in Tibet, The PLAAF would presently face serious problems of surviving a battle against India. However, the advent of the new generation fighters like Su-30 MKK, J-10, J-11, J-20, air refuelling capabilities, airborne radar and an improved air defence system will further improve China's capabilities in the coming years and will prove to be a threat worth reckoning with.

Analysis with respect to the aspects of quality and quantity of the production capabilities of the Aviation industries of both, China and India, and India's role in the changing geopolitics in the region under preview of current rise of China, is viewed both in terms of threat as well as an opportunity. While India must accept the inevitable rise of China as a challenge but, at the same time also prepare to leverage greater influence on other nations in the region to maintain the balance of power, which would help India address its security dilemma. Hence, while both China and India in their own interest must build capabilities, they must also accept the fact that the future order in Asia will have the capacity to absorb the aspirations of both the countries concurrently. However, Indian policy makers must chip-in and provide greater impetus to defence, building military capabilities not only through imports but also by the process of indigenization and thus reverse the extremely skewed self-reliance index. If India wants to elevate its status and leverage greater influence in the evolving new order in Asia, it would not only require increasing its military capability but also expanding its self-reliance as well as intellectual capacity that is required to combat the threat of an emerging regional power.

Changes in the PLAAF doctrine and concepts have had an effect on the development of an advanced industrial and technological base. China has for long been trying to develop its indigenous defence industry because of the realisation that foreign countries will not part with critical technology. To develop its own industry, China has spent many resources on R&D and on procuring Western technology illegally, by cyber-attack, espionage and finding loopholes in western sanctions for dual use technology. As a result of these steps, the Chinese aviation made good progress in all fields except aero-engines and fire control radars. These shortcomings are being addressed, and China is reported to be investing in aero-engine R&D to cover this technological gap.

Conclusion

From the Indian stand-point, the ineptitude on the part of the government to

capitalise on the knowledge generated by rising industrialization is glaring evidence. Hence, despite being amongst the top ten defence spenders in the world, India continues to procure over 70 percent of its equipment needs from abroad. As a result, India is unable to extract the maximum benefit for its economic growth. Nevertheless, if India at all wants to reverse this imbalance and in future compete with China, it would have to bring about innovative and creative reforms. India will rapidly have to shift focus from acquiring platforms to developing capabilities, absorb R&D as an integral part of the system by focussing on components in the denial list and look at R&D from a long-term perspective as an investment for future growth. The industry will need to strategize by becoming a part of the global supply chain which will not only invigorate the aviation industry as a whole but also bring along with it better management and financial practices, improve efficiency and produce better quality products for the end user.

India's reaction to reforms in China's aviation industry and its progress in military modernisation is a natural response by any growing superpower. China is merely exercising its legitimate right to modernise and guarantee its national security by preparing for asymmetric operations firstly against the 'state-of-the-art' military powers which would automatically prepare China against any other rising power in the evolving world order, and India too could strategize for the future. From the Indian perspective, the rise of China's military must also be viewed as a driver to spur India's future military capability and capacities.

China's rise by default has drawn out a roadmap for India's military strategy and modernisation and, hence it is now upto India, to maximise from the opportunity and narrow the gap in military capabilities between the two countries. Therefore, China's rise has to be clearly and closely monitored by India. India, like China is at an advantage, with its economy expected to grow at 7-8 percent based on strong fundamentals, robust institutions, vibrant democratic system, and is largely perceived as an attractive market by investors across the globe. India needs to be cautious about China's continuous increase in military budget, which would widen the gap in its capability and, as a result, create greater asymmetry between China and India. Therefore, India needs to strategize in the coming decade, look at its military expenditure as a long-term investment which will not only invigorate growth in the aviation sector but also, place India in a position of advantage with the changing geopolitics in the region.

Recommendations

After exhaustive exposure to the various aspects related to Chinese aviation

industry as well as Indian aviation industry, the following recommendations to boost the Indian aviation industry can be considered.

- (a) Transparency of the work culture of the various government-run R&D institutes needs to improve. People need to be made accountable for long delays in rolling out key projects. The 'blame game' so inherent to the government institutes needs to stop immediately and the focus should shift towards creating a healthy atmosphere in the industry. Policies of either perform or perish have to be followed to compete in the open market at a global level.
- (b) Departmental procedures and willingness to share information between the Government organisations like DRDO labs as well as private partners like L&T, Bharat Forge, etc. need to improve. In case, DRDO continues to hold essential data required for R&D by private partners, under the clause of confidentiality, private groups will ultimately choke and vanish from the Indian Aviation Industry in no time. If required, a nominal consultancy fee can be charged to the private firm by the DRDO labs but exchange of essential information for development and progress of this sector should and must be shared.
- (c) Hegemony of PSUs like HAL, BEL needs to be stopped immediately. On close interaction with different private firms who have finished developing their products, it is often found that they are still waiting for certification and field trials. Procedural delay in certification leads to huge financial losses, which means a lot to the private firms, where they are accountable to their shareholders and investors. Departmental hurdles by our 'White Elephants' need to be removed for this industry to survive and have fair a chance in this competition. Such is the level of juxtapose, that for each and every certification, all private defence firms have to approach DRDO, who are the nodal agency under MOD. The rising level of discomfort which has risen in various DRDO labs as well as PSUs like HAL & BEL, since the entry of private firms into defence manufacturing is no secret to anybody. Under such conditions, putting these private partners under indirect approval and a farcical certification game is akin to pleading non-guilty in front of hungry Lions. In case the interference of PSUs and DRDO in the acquisition process is not removed, all the private players will end up losing all their money to lengthy and tedious evaluation and the certification game and finally Hegemony of DRDO and PSUs will prevail as it was before and no progress will be seen in this sector.

- (d) Rules and regulations regarding export of Indigenous defence products needs to be eased. This will provide a wider customer base to our private industry, wherein they do not have to totally rely on the Indian Armed Forces for their orders. At the same time, with better revenues from their sale abroad, they will be able to consolidate their position in the global market and hence will project a strong global appeal for Indian aviation products.
- (e) Interaction between R&D, the manufacturer and finally the end user is the major grey area, right now. It was a glaring fact that R&D done by research labs has very little sight into the tactical applications of the project they are working on. User Interface was missing during the entire process of R&D and even manufacture. This interface has been the primary stimuli of the growing mistrust between users and the manufacturing agencies, wherein the user will always have a greater inclination towards products from a foreign manufacturer than indigenously manufactured products due to this glaring discrepancy in indigenous products. Close interaction between the user and the manufacturer, during the different stages of development will reduce the flaws and shortcoming which are likely to come out during field trials and also infuse confidence in the users.
- (f) Quality assurance of our indigenous aviation products is an issue, which keeps troubling our aviation industry perpetually all the time. The refusal of the French to validate the guarantee on the Indian manufactured 'Rafale' fighter was considered as a major thaw in the entire deal. We cannot blame the French for this, because we know our fault lines, which we have not been able to correct in the last almost five decades. Finally, accountability needs to improve and people should be held responsible for poor workmanship and quality control, irrespective of the seniority of their positions or their political connections. We can no longer lose lives of potential users to faulty products by our PSUs. These faulty products, apart from costing precious lives, and thus our prestige also, give a poor name to the Aviation Industry of our country.
- (g) The advent of the new Defence Procurement Policy (DPP) and Defence Procurement Manual (DPM) 2016, the formal introduction of 'Make in India' and giving a top priority to indigenously "Designed, Developed & Manufactured" products is a welcome step by the new government. Defence R&D is a costly affair for any private player. Private firms are responsible to their shareholders and require influx of regular capital to

sustain themselves in a highly competitive market. Hence, private firms are looking for firm orders from the Indian Designed Developed & Manufactured (IDDM) may sound good on paper, but it is a regular and assured supply order, which is vital for sustenance. Otherwise, private defence firms will close down with the same speed in which they actually opened.

- (h) HAL has to grow itself beyond LCA. Upgradation of LCA has to gain momentum to keep pace with the evolving aviation technology and Air Force needs. Observations made by its primary users, i.e. IAF need to be addressed on a priority basis.
- (i) Realistic execution towards Indigenous Fighter projects like the AMCA (Advanced Medium Combat Aircraft) need to be expedited; otherwise, the project will suffer indefinite delays and eventually turn into a tug of war between the manufacturer and the User, similar in lines to its predecessor LCA.
- (j) Though recommendations of Committee on Requirement vs. Feasibility of Fifth Generation Fighter Aircraft (FGFA) for IAF are yet to be opened in public domain, still on hindsight, if India still wants to pursue its FGFA without Russian Assistance, experienced and proficient manpower needs to be enrolled on a priority basis, who have the capability and can roll out projects of that significance. Leaving it purely on HAL and DRDO will take the project back by at least another 20 years which is definitely not in favour of INDIA.

Notes

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